

THE BLACK IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF VENDA NOVA DO IMIGRANTE: A HISTORY OF CHALLENGES AND OVERCOME

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme that discusses the black population in Venda Nova do Imigrante, ES. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it presents to the academic environment the possibility of deeper studies on the presence of these individuals from very early on in the occupation of the Brazilian territory and in the mountainous region of the state of Espírito Santo, present in the coffee plantations and in the opening of roads. Its social relevance lies in the condition of expanding knowledge about the struggles and conflicts between ethnic groups. This is a bibliographical research, based on discourse analysis as an instrument for interpreting the thought exposed in the consulted works. Constructing a positive, solid black identity in a society that, historically, teaches blacks from a very early age that to be accepted it is necessary to deny oneself, proves to be a very heavy challenge to be faced by blacks and women. black Brazilians. What highlights, pedagogically and didactically, is that, at school, are teachers and trainers aware of this issue? Could it be that education, as a path to the integral formation of man, as a means of preparing for full citizenship, incorporates this reality in a serious and responsible way? There is no disagreement that, as the former black slaves were in miserable conditions, they accepted to work for those who owned something, donated by the Brazilian State, in exchange for food and shelter and were exploited again, now in a less perverse way to the eyes of the [so-called] humanists. The issue of the presence, even of prejudice against blacks, in Brazil, is due to the ideological discourse, in which, in order to justify the dehumanizing condition of slavery against equals, in the sense of understanding that they are human beings, the Catholic Church disseminated the idea that they had in their soul. By this term, it is understood, they do not think, do not feel, do not abstract; they are things and so they reified a whole group of people, indistinctly.

Keywords: New Immigrant Sale. Black identity. Ethnic conflict.

INTRODUCTION

The situation of the black population in Brazil is still marked by various types of violence, even after more than a century has passed since the end of the slave regime. This can be felt in many ways, whether in the expression of jokes, stories, anecdotes, racism in different ways.

Africans, in the sixteenth century and beyond, were forcibly uprooted from their territory, brought, in subhuman conditions, to a strange land in which, shortly after their arrival, they were deprived of [almost] all of their natural rights as the freedom and dignity. They also lost the right to assume their identities as subjects and in such a process they resisted. Even after the shackles of the slave regime were broken and, in the middle of the 21st century, abolition was not enough to guarantee this group due recognition as subjects of rights. This is because the social condition of the black population in Brazil is still marked by precariousness, in various political aspects, in addition to the everyday racism that excludes these people from the possibility of feeling like they belong to the society in which Eurocentric aesthetic and social values and standards prevail. .

The issue of social belonging is a complex situation, because belonging means *being part of*, being inserted, being recognized as an element of that particular group. It is not about enjoying absolute rights; it is an experience that is part of human existence, that is, that human beings yearn to be part of a society (GOMES, 2007); it is not a wish, it is far beyond that. It means that, as social actors, any existence outside this scope of the human existential conjuncture is unthinkable , considering that it is in the context of culture and history that individuals build and affirm their social identities (all of them, and not just racial identity). . Therefore, recognizing oneself in an identity presupposes responding, affirmatively, to a question from a certain group and establishing a broad sense of belonging to a reference social group. In this process, nothing is simple or stable, as these multiple identities can demand, at the same time, different, divergent, or even contradictory loyalties. This is where a game of conflicts and beliefs comes in that leads individuals to decide who they are and to which group they actually belong, not only in terms of phenotypic characterization, but also ideologically. The civilized human being is, sociologically, the subject of many identities and these multiple social identities can also be provisionally attractive, later seeming disposable; they can then be rejected and abandoned (GOMES, 2017), according to the political-ideological commitment to which they come to be a part.

In the conception of Gomes (2017), black identity should be about an achievement,

something that is gradually built, in a movement that involves numerous variables, causes and effects, from the first relationships established in the most intimate social group (which is the family and those who are closest to them), in which personal contacts are always established permeated by sanctions and also by affectivities and where the first tests of a future vision of the world are elaborated. Generally, this process begins in the family and creates ramifications and developments from the other relationships that the subject establishes. However, during slavery it was common for the children of blacks to be separated from their parents, being sold or even taken to other parts, where their education ignored the humanizing condition and forming bonds with the original family culture. In this sense, the identity that was formed was abstract, even if it was a black entity. The understanding that black identity is understood here as a social, historical, cultural and plural construction is not lost. It implies the construction of the look of an ethnic/racial group or of subjects who belong to the same ethnic/racial group, about themselves, from the relationship with the other (GOMES, 2017).

With regard to women, especially in the colonial period, they were conceived as a human being inferior to men. Thus, being a black woman represented a double challenge in relation to prejudice and social belonging. “Inserted in this context are black women slaves, who were [*at that specific moment*] placed at a lower social level, both for being a woman and for being black and also a slave” (SILVA, 2010, p. 03). This is a treatment condition that was given to these women, simply for being who they were: women, black and subject to the slavery regime. These were criteria for being considered targets of prejudice and discrimination that have extended to the present day, sometimes in a veiled way; but, which persist in everyday actions and which prove to be difficult to solve.

Brazilian thinkers at the end of the 19th century, influenced by European eugenic ideas and later by the *social Darwinism* of H. Spencer (1820-1903), built a structure of thought and interpretations that remains rooted in social thought. As soon as,

To be a woman, and to be a slave within an extremely prejudiced, oppressive and sexist society, is to gather all the elements favorable to exploitation, both economic and sexual, and also to be the target of humiliation by society in its different segments (SILVA, 2010, p. .03).

As a way of understanding the existence of all prejudice built in the past, it is necessary to know the roots of racism towards the black population in Brazil. An example of this is the fact that African and Afro-Brazilian culture is inserted in almost all of Brazil: traditions, cultural manifestations, heroes and heroines, resistance; however, this legacy is still muted. Stories of black women who fought against slavery and racism are still unknown by most of Brazilian

society.

As a symbol of this struggle, Silva (2010) will argue that the examples of vindictive women who sought social mobility and the right to continue enjoying their freedom are not isolated cases and to exemplify this social battle, the emblematic case of the Creole can be consulted. Gertrudes in, who, after being manumitted, saw her freedom project threatened when she had to go to court to prove her status as a freedman, waging a legal battle against the creditors of her former master who demanded her as payment for a debt contracted by the same, as if she had any connection with the problem. This marks racism, when many understood it as inadmissible that blacks, especially females, could enjoy the full right to civil freedom. asserting their natural rights. The aforementioned example is just one among others that can be explored in the literature on the subject. Gomes (2002), will address this aspect of belonging, analyzing it from a pedagogical perspective and argues that,

Belonging or not to an ethnic/racial segment makes a lot of difference in the relationships established between school subjects, in the evaluation moments, in the expectations built around school performance and in the way differences are treated. Although official curricula are now gradually incorporating critical readings about the situation of blacks, and some teachers are committed to working with the racial issue in the school environment, hair and other diacritical marks are still used as a criterion to discriminate between blacks, whites and mestizos . The issue of black aesthetic expression is still not considered a topic to be discussed by Brazilian pedagogy (GOMES, 2002, p. 45).

The author makes a specific analysis on the issue of Pedagogy, but there are themes that, due to their interdisciplinary nature, should be addressed in all fields of knowledge, especially in the Human Sciences, where studies of inter-relational conflicts and extra -relational, as part of its scope. Aesthetics is linked to beauty and must be directly linked to the human and its various conformations, which would require deep anthropological studies and with the least possible bias of passion.

The author goes on to argue that comparative treatments should be carried out between cultures and their diversities, because, in her view, reviewing

It is in these spaces that opportunities for comparison, the presence of other aesthetic standards, lifestyles and cultural practices gain prominence in the daily life of black children and adolescents, often in a way contrary to what is learned in the family. In some cases, it is the mother's care, the way the child is seen in the family environment, that enable him to build a positive self-representation about being black (GOMES, 2002, p. 46).

The reaction of each black person to prejudice is very particular. And, this particularity

is closely linked to the construction of black identity and the possibilities of socialization and information (GOMES, 2002). In this sense, not a single chapter in the history of black people in Brazil can be ignored, especially to remember those who took part in the atrocities and why they did so, the consequences for the black population; especially for black women.

The entire history of black people needs to be remembered for the understanding that one should not classify someone by the color of their skin, or by their hair, rather, by values, culture, by the potential of their work, by the resistance in their history, for their experiences, which were not reported in history books.

Gomes (2017) will argue that building a positive, solid black identity in a society that, historically, teaches black people, from a very early age, that to be accepted you have to deny yourself, is a very challenging challenge. heavy to be faced by black men and women in Brazil.

What highlights, pedagogically and didactically, is that, at school, are teachers and trainers aware of this issue? Could it be that education, as a path to the integral formation of men, as a means of preparing for full citizenship, incorporates this reality in a serious and responsible way, when discussing, in the processes of teacher training, the importance of cultural diversity? To understand the construction of black identity in Brazil, it is also important to consider it not only in its subjective and symbolic dimension; but, above all, in its political sense and by this term, we can understand social, in the broadest imaginable way (GOMES, 2017).

This feeling of not belonging is even worse when black individuals are inserted in a context where they represent minorities, as is the case of the city of Venda Nova do Imigrante, state of Espírito Santo, where colonization took place through Italians, immigrants who lived there. established themselves at the end of the 19th century.

THE STORY OF THE NEW IMMIGRANT SALE: BEFORE AND AFTER THE ITALIANS ARRIVAL

In the year 1988, more precisely on May 10th, the municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante was born, south in the state of Espírito Santo in the southeastern region of the country. Being predominantly Italian colonized, which occurred around the end of the 19th century, during the imperial government's propaganda to attract Europeans, in order to whiten the Brazilian population, an idea much defended by Oliveira Viana (1883-1951) who believed that Brazil's backwardness was due to black people and not to slavery (DÁVILA, 2006).

According to the IBGE survey (2010 census), the population in this city is

predominantly white and, as already suggested above, certain stereotypes remain implied in the collective imagination of the population, which conceives Italian culture as the only one existing in the municipality.

However, history points out that, in the process of colonization of the territory of Venda Nova do Imigrante, other peoples were also present. On the website of the Municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante, there is the following description about the colonization:

The Municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante, created on May 10, 1988, through Decree Law nº 4069 (of 06-05-88), dismembering Conceição do Castelo. It began to be colonized around 1892, basically by Italian immigrants, whose culture remains alive in their descendants and in the life of the Vendanovense community. However, long before the region was inhabited by Indians, probably Puris, of whom many objects were found by the first wave of immigrants. The community that emerged with the arrival of the first immigrants in 1892, retains strong traits of their culture, especially the community and progressive spirit. With the abolition of slavery, Italian immigrants, originally from the Veneto Region (Italy), attracted by the search for land in the localities of São Pedro do Araguaia, Matilde, São Martinho and Carolina, initially around 18 to 20 families, among them: Perim, Caliman, Zandonadi, Altoé, Bragato, Venturim, Falcheto, Brioschi, Sossai, Carnielli, Cola, Minetti, Lorenzoni, Delpupo, Tonolli, Ambrozim, Scabello, Mazzoco, Fioreze and Mascarello, came to be allocated in the region (CITY HALL DE VENDA NOVA DO IMIGRANTE, 2020, p. 01).

From the text available on the official website of the town hall of Venda Nova do Imigrante, it is possible to identify the presence of different peoples who were part of the colonization process of the municipality, namely: indigenous, black and white (Italians).

According to Falchetto (2017), the Colônia Castello in São Pedro de Araguaia in Espírito Santo (ES) was the first place of residence after the arrival of the immigrants. The Italians promptly observed that those lands were unsuitable for cultivation, which they called *lean land*. During this period, they were informed about productive land in the Alto Castelo region, in which they would take possession of land and former slave farms. Note the existence of a black ex-slave population in the region. This leads to understanding the participation of blacks in the history of the municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante; certainly, many have remained in these territories until the present day. In addition, they preserved elements of their cultures that are not valued when talking about traditions characteristic of this municipality, given the invisibility of Afro-Brazilian culture in this region.

Faced with the search for more productive lands, the Italians moved to another territory where they founded the Colony of Venda Nova, reconfiguring the history of the region as one of the most promising municipalities and one of the greatest icons of Italian culture in the Centro-Mountain Region of Espírito Santo. Santo, as well as the municipality of Santa Teresa

and the district of Aracê, in the community of Pedra Azul, located in Domingos Martins.

The author of the book *The Hidden Treasure* (2017), brings the importance of the São Pedro de Alcântara Road, which is currently known as the Imperial Route of the Estrada Real, built by the imperial government to connect Vitória, which crosses the municipalities of Venda Nova do Imigrante, Conceição de Castle and Muniz Freire. According to Leal (2016), in his article *The Imperial Route of the Estrada Real: The Estrada São Pedro de Alcântara*:

The barracks spaced along the road were sometimes changed in location, or even deactivated definitively. Initially, they were: Cachoeiro do Rio Santa Maria (Depósito Geral in Santa Leopoldina, Bragança Pinhel, Serpa, Ouré, Barcelos, Vila Viçosa, Monforte, Souzel, Chaves, Santa Cruz and Vila do Príncipe, all names of cities in Portugal, being shortly afterwards, the Borba and Melgaço ones were created (LEAL, 2016, p. 06).

The author is also based on the stories he heard from different sources, through characters to reconstitute the past of the region before the arrival of the Italians from Núcleo Castello and Alfredo Chaves. One of these characters, fundamental in this context is O Velho Januário. Well known, he had a good appearance despite his 60 (sixty) years old, strong, friendly and polite caboclo, at the time an employee of the Imperial Court and made periodic trips from Vitória (ES) to Ouro Preto (MG). His job was to conduct the letters that arrived from Portugal to their final destination, the capital of Minas Gerais. These anonymous, non-white heroes who contributed to the development of the region already existed before the arrival of the Italians.

Falchetto (2017) rescues the occupation of immigrants in the old town of Venda Nova do Imigrante and the origins of volunteer work, such as the solidarity gesture of some immigrants such as: Marmim Zandonadi, Domingos Perim and other Italians with surnames considered traditional in the Vendanovense community. In the book, the author gives little emphasis to women in the process of building the municipality. The importance of women appears in volunteer work after the Spanish flu epidemic in 1919.

The work states the number of Italian families, as can be seen in the section where it mentions that, when “it was already inhabited by about 30 to 40 families of Italian immigrants, typhoid fever broke out, which spread throughout the region reaching almost all families (...)”, this excerpt exemplifies the forgetfulness of black families in this period of epidemic.

Families less affected by the epidemic or that recovered first helped those who were still sick: harvesting coffee, planting corn, doing household chores, in everything that was possible to help and without charging anything. It is understood that domestic work at that time was exclusively carried out by women; however, the lexicon woman was subtracted from the

previous section and concludes that there is an invisibility of the female figure in this account.

The former Venda Nova, during the slave trade, is refounded and known as São Pedro de Venda Nova, a tribute to the first place when they arrived from Italy São Pedro de Araguaia, in Alfredo Chaves. At the end of the 19th century and beginning of the 20th century, in the Espírito Santo region, the city is rebuilt amidst the ruins and on the banks of the Imperial Road. During the restoration process, they found an old mansion that was used by former miners and other road users, which later became the district of Conceição do Castelo and finally came to be municipalized.¹⁰

The author makes an overview of the diaries of Bishop D. Pedro de Lacerda, from 1880 and 1886, in order to understand the history of the municipalities of Conceição do Castelo and the municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante, which was dismembered at that time. It was remarkable for the people of the region, as the search for gold caught the attention of adventurers and robbers of all kinds, coming mainly from Minas Gerais, circulating along the Imperial Road. Zandonadi (2019), also recalls the settlement of Puris Indians. According to Rocha (2016) who gives a brief report on the Aldemento Imperial Afonsino, created in 1846 by the provincial government and managed by priests Frei Bento de Genoa and Frei Daniel de Nápoles, to allocate the aforementioned ethnic group, where it is currently located. known as the municipality of Conceição do Castelo.

According to Rocha (1979), the indigenous villages,

It differed little from a slave camp; Persistently hunted like wild beasts, the Puris tried to escape those who tried to subdue them. the Puris Indians were commonly employed in the painful service of building roads and in military detachments destined to chase runaway slaves (ROCHA,1979, p. 52).

The construction of the São Pedro de Alcântara Road lasted more than two years according to the book *The Hidden Treasure*, the result of research carried out by Mr. Benjamim Falchetto. In 1816, it was already possible to travel on foot; but it was after 4 (four) years that the first herd was brought to Vitória, on June 22, 1820, driven by the cowherd driver Antônio Alexandre Elci Câmara and was received with acclamation by the people. In the Royal Charter of December 4, 1820, the said road was declared ready.

The book describes the first impacts when the first Italian immigrants arrived in this area of land, which inhabited Tupi and Botocudo Indians, who ended up being taken by force for manual labor in the construction of roads. The Indians and blacks living here were turned

¹⁰These are souvenirs brought by Anna Zandonadi, resident of the old building, when she arrived with her family descended from Colonia Castello, Alfredo Chaves. Personal communication.

into slaves so that, finally, the long-awaited progress would come along with the emergence of roads.

The author describes the difficulties of the first immigrants in this land of Venda Nova:

Here they found four abandoned farms, fertile but inhospitable land, wild nature, isolated from the rest of the civilized world, far from commerce, without roads and means of communication. To survive, they had to join hands and build everything together: houses, church, schools, roads and bridges. Everything was done in a joint effort (FALCHETTO, 2017, p. 27).

Local economic growth proved to be extremely necessary and families began to grow and children needed to study. Behold, in the year 1921 the first school appears so that the children of the city's residents could be literate; it was just a classroom where students big and small studied together from first to fourth grade, in the same room in what we know today as schools with multigrade classes. As soon as they finished the 4th school year, they had to work in the fields until the army was called up, as military service was mandatory.

During this period, Venda Nova became the ferment of religious vocations and almost all families had boys and girls studying in religious schools. The recruiters of the Divine Word Congregation belonged to the Marist Brothers, the Salesians, the Augustinians and the SVDs. Many students followed new paths and others returned with expanded knowledge, thus building music and theater schools. They started cooperativism, associativism and volunteering, leading Venda Nova to national prominence.

The author, in robust words, declares that the place becomes a center of culture in a land where only uneducated people existed, what was Pantanal in the middle of the Atlantic Forest became the Garden of the mountains in the state of Espírito Santo. In 2017, Venda Nova has the highest rate of university students and people with higher education among more than 5500 municipalities, in addition to the *per capita income* being equal to Ribeirão Preto (SP), one of the highest in the country. These numbers prove that many young people were attending universities in 2017; but, we will return to 81 years ago to understand who the teachers were at that time and Venda Nova (FALCHETTO, 2017).

Dona Rita, mother of João Barcelos, was a very good lady, who, despite being prostrate and at an advanced age, would go to the house of the students' parents to do the most humble tasks, such as washing and ironing, and would ask for nothing in exchange for her work, inferior services. which part Italian women didn't want to do. He states, in his statements, that Italians, in general, lived away from blacks who, according to Italian culture and their different customs, considered such an attitude not an expression of racism, since the Barcelos family, which was

made up of blacks, never had been neglected (FALCHETTO, 2017).

Imperial Law No. 3,353, sanctioned on May 13, 1888, which became known as *Lei Áurea*, made it clear that whipping and the sale of blacks would be prohibited; therefore, they would become free with this law, but without the right to land, houses, food and school; they were only free after the abolition of slavery (FALCHETTO, 2017). The referred author argues that most of the newly freed blacks returned to the condition of slaves.

It is notorious for Luana Santos (2010) that blacks were not freed, inferring that,

Even with the advent of the abolition of slavery in 1888, following the Proclamation of the Republic, socioeconomic structures in Brazil remained practically unchanged. Although *free*, *men and women of color* remained in *captivity*, in a permanent state of marginalization, misery and abandonment (SANTOS, 2010, p. 29).

Dona Rita, amid so many challenges of being a woman and black, raised her children to be teachers. Her first son became a teacher and was called João Barcelos, during this period the woman and black woman assumes an important role within the municipality, the teacher Leonidia who assumes the position as soon as her brother is transferred and her family continues to live in the city. school (FALCHETTO, 2017).

About the presence of black Africans in Espírito Santo territory, Cleber Maciel will report that,

In the territory of Espírito Santo in the 19th century, enslaved Africans could be found together with transferred blacks, mainly from Bahia and other regions of the Northeast, Rio de Janeiro and Minas Gerais, including the post-republican migratory movement. This means that in order to understand the origin of black people from Espírito Santo in the 20th century, one must also consider the migratory movement of black groups that arrived from other regions of the country and the various miscegenations that occurred over time (MACIEL, 2016, p. 29).

What the author clarifies and which must be understood without any passion is that the coastal strip of the Province of Espírito Santo received blacks from Africa since the mid-16th century; However, inland, away from the coast, especially in the Mountainous Region, it was only in the 19th century that occupations were more coordinated with the country's interiorization policy.

According to Maciel (2016),

Historians are unanimous in stating that the Capitania do Espírito Santo was one of those that smuggled the most slaves. In addition, they claim that it is almost impossible, nowadays, to pinpoint with absolute certainty the origin of black people from Espírito Santo (MACIEL, 2016, p. 63).

The author continues his explanation by quoting Novaes (1963, pp. 23-26)¹¹, where this researcher states that “it is suspected that because of the slave revolts that took place in São Mateus, Guarapari, Serra and in the Itapemirim area, it was very significant the presence of Sudanese Muslims in these regions” (MACIEL, 2016, p. 64).

Another contribution of great value to this archaeological mystery about the origin of the black people who were brought to Brazil and the negotiations between sugar mill and coffee lords is the one due to Senhor Rui Barbosa (1849-1923), who as soon as he assumed the chair of Minister of Finance ordered to set fire to the documents about the blacks that were in that building.

Specifically on the black population in Espírito Santo, Maciel (2016) argues that,

It is very important to remember that the total number of slaves in Espírito Santo in 1887 was 13,382 people. Therefore, it can be said that this was the minimum number of black people, since there were no white slaves. As after almost no more systematic information about people's color, it is difficult to know how the census mobility of the black population was after the end of slavery. If before 1888 the data were inaccurate, after that date they became much more so, because most surveys on the number of people did not refer to skin color. [...] After 1888, without slavery, it was almost impossible to know the minimum number of blacks. In fact, it even seemed that blacks were 'disappearing' among so many whites who arrived through the great European immigration (MACIEL, 2016, pp. 72-3).

This situation portrayed by Cleber Maciel is a danger, from the historical point of view and in terms of identity, because as there was a generalized depreciation of black people and the desire to whiten the population, it was even natural for statistics to publish their results in this way .

An entire ideological machinery for denying even the existence of the population was black was thought of and applied as part of the eugenic model to *Tupiniquim* and it did not work, but the effects persist throughout the history of the nation in which discrimination persists as a historical mark of their condition of life, in which they are minorities in all political fields of organized social life.

When one thinks of gender divisions (men and women), nothing changes, nothing more than a euphemism, because in the end it is the entire black population that finds itself on the margins of opportunities, not because they were slaves, which is another understatement; this situation has been in the past for more than a century and if it has not been overcome until

¹¹NOVAES, Maria Stella de. *Slavery and abolition in Espírito Santo*. History and Folklore. Victory. Literary and Scientific Award from the Legislative Assembly of the State of Espírito Santo. 1963, p. 23 to 26.

today, it is because of intellectual incompetence on the one hand and lack of character on the other, who still want to explain a political fraud by the State against a population group through of a system already abolished.

Maciel narrates in his work that,

A German scientist, Ernest Wagemann ¹², who studied the colony of his countrymen in Espírito Santo in 1913, reported that among the German colonists the most predominant form of land acquisition worked as follows: there were many locations in the interior where the natives were already living, , almost always black, who owned a piece of land, with some boundary stakes and a small house, where they hunted and felled and burned the bush for banana, coffee, cassava and bean plantations. Under these conditions, they were living somewhat isolated as if they were still in quilombos, fleeing slavery. Then came the immigrants or their descendants who saw in those lands, already cleared and with some improvements, a business opportunity. Thus, using the most diverse artifices, they ended up expelling the blacks who went in search of new areas. After taking over the land, the immigrants increased the felling, expanded the limits and plantations and, using the benefits of the laws, regularized the possessions, transforming them into their properties (MACIEL, 2016, p. 113).

What this Chilean of German origin, who came to Brazil to research about German immigrants in *Terra Brasilis Tupiniquins* and who must have barely left his hotel room, in Praia do Canto, that is, he did not go to talk to any German who was chipping in the middle of the bush, facing the wild rudeness of the Brazilian wild nature, he wrote what they told him, because this was an obligation assumed by the Brazilian State, because they went to Europe and made misleading advertisements of the same carat that they did to the northeastern people of the semi-arid region. arid to come to work in the Industry in São Paulo.

There is no disagreement that, as the former black slaves were in miserable conditions, they accepted to work for those who owned something, donated by the Brazilian State, in exchange for food and shelter and were exploited again, now in a less perverse way to the eyes of [*so-called*] humanists. What we actually have is nothing more than the exchange of one type of slavery for another, in which the individual's body was exploited, without becoming absolute owner of it.

Gomes (2002), will argue, from this clash that,

When we think of enslaved Africans brought to Brazil, the process of objectification of the slave materialized in the social relations of that historical

¹²Ernest Wagemann was born on February 18, 1884, in Chañarcillo, Chile, died on March 20, 1956, in Bad Godesberg, Germany. He was a very active political economist and statistician in Germany from the 1920s onwards, being the founder of the Institute for Economic Research (1925), later called the German Institute for Economic Research, and in 1932 he launched the Wagemann Plan to combat the economic crisis. In 1948, back in Chile, he worked as a teacher, returning to Germany in 1953 (ESTAÇÃO CAPIXABA, 2015, p. 01).

moment always comes to mind. This process was objectified not only in the slave condition, but in the way the masters related to the body of the slaves and how they treated them: corporal punishment, whipping, iron brands, mutilation of the body, sexual abuse are some examples of this treatment. Even in the face of such a situation, in which official freedom was conditioned to the letter of manumission, male and female slaves developed the most diverse forms of rebellion, resistance and pursuit of freedom (GOMES, 2002, p. 57).

The author draws attention here to the problem of the subjugation of the spirit by indoctrination and crushing of the individual's body, because it is through this that he can problematize his intrinsic and extrinsic problems and, again, the question of sex (man and woman) in the slave regime is lost, because the problem posed was not related to this detail, but to a question of skin color, the expression of a genealogical phenotype that there was no way to defend or disguise. The only thing that gender will determine there is the type of aggression to which this body will be subjected, not necessarily whether or not it will be attacked.

C. Maciel (2016) explains that,

With the end of slavery, all workers became free and entitled to receive wages. However, as has already been said, many of the old masters sent their black workers away, considering that from then on they were free, they provided work only for the whites. In cases where blacks were hired, usually the bosses only accepted them paying much less than what was paid to whites for the same work. In the absence of work and because of the need to survive to feed their families, many blacks agreed to earn less. But they were extremely exploited, humiliated and, with no way to improve their lives, they were persecuted by the police and deceived by politicians. At the same time, immigrants were prospering, earning or buying land, receiving support from businessmen and politicians, in addition to government facilities (MACIEL, 2016, p. 114).

These property owners admitted blacks because of the incompetence of whites to manage production systems, because the speech of Oliveira Viana (1883-1951) and other eugenicists was that the mere presence of whites on farms already raised productivity themselves, that is, the question of mastering the technique, skills with the business were not in question and many people believed in this, until they found themselves tight and without income, with the enterprises collapsing, which forced them to hire who dominated the production system, however, in conditions more or as precarious as it was in the era of slavery.

Many of the current capixaba blacks are working in services that pay low wages, such as building construction works, in loading and unloading services for trucks, trains and ships, in the lower ranks of the military police, in private security services, in construction services, cleaning and maintenance of works in cities, in heavy rural work, in domestic services and in the worst wages in industries and commerce (MACIEL, 2016, p. 115).

The issue of slavery and the terrible living conditions to which blacks were condemned after the Abolition of Slavery in May 1888 is not due to them and in many cases, they were not expelled from the properties by mere malice on the part of the landowners. It is much more a State Policy. For example, in Laranja da Terra, Leopoldino, O Bravo, when he received the news of the abolition, in 1895, donated a piece of land to his former slaves, now freed, so that they could continue with their lives with dignity (SOUZA, 2012). However, there was government aid to European immigrants and farmers who hired this white workforce; benefit that did not extend to those who used black labor.

Along with this, there was a whole political propaganda, in which farmers were discouraged from hiring these individuals who, until a few days ago, were responsible for the production of their properties and enterprises. It's a contrast, because the Europeans who arrived in Brazil didn't even know what coffee, crops, large livestock was. How could they innovate and expand production, without any mastery of the technique? Whereas they didn't even know her, in fact.

As for these freed black individuals, how could they request financial help from development agencies to carry out their projects and undertakings? Faced with this rudeness that the Positive Law imposed on itself, the only thing left was the search for an answer at the bottom of a bottle of cachaça, since I could not find it in any other worthy place. The State created a perverse policy regarding these individuals and, as a way of avoiding historical guilt for what it was causing now, to free men, it created pejorative speeches against these people.

This format of depreciation of someone who was once part of everyday life, took care of children, educated them, watched over their safety and, suddenly, is transformed into a demon to be exorcised even from the nation, as if they were monsters, provoked the great collapse and the formation of a socially marginalized group that, after that, never recovered with the due dignity to which they deserve.

The woman, of African descent, is not as subservient as the European, in which her function was to give birth and take care of the children. In Africa, due to its tribal system, women, from an early age, see themselves on the verge of, in addition to taking care of domestic tasks and the offspring, they are obliged to negotiate, manage family assets, land, animals, crops and to defend their homes (FISCHER, 2006).

And it was no different in Brazil, where even enslaved, they did not lose their command of situations and positions of struggle in favor of their identities as women and mothers. The problem, once again, revolves around the deconstruction of an identity that inevitably leads to

the construction of a personality ontologically disconnected from its roots.

Gomes (2002) expands the discussion on the issue of the body and its relationship with slavery, putting into discussion that,

If the body speaks about our being in the world, the slave's historical relationship with the body expresses much more than the idea of submission, insistently preached by society at the time and which echoes in our ears to this day. Has the school given another reading to this relationship? Or do black and white children, when they study the racial issue, still participate in the representation of the black body only as a whipped and chained body? Could it be that today, in the middle of the third millennium, the textbooks and discussions on the history of black people in Brazil carried out by the school highlight that the black body, since the time of slavery, has always been a contesting body? (GOMES, 2002, p. 89).

If the author poses this question, it is because the answer has already been given to anyone interested in research on the subject, because that is how it works; a narrative of negation is created about the other, hiding a particularity that is the most powerful in this being and from its ontology it is denied together with him. Many were the corporal violations suffered by black women, simply because that way, it was believed that they would no longer exercise power over men and women.

CONCLUSION

The situation of the black population in Brazil is a field of effervescent political studies and its exploration depends on deepening the themes in places where slave exploitation systems occurred, in order to understand the development of actions in favor of blacks after the abolition of slavery and how they survived the campaigns of denial of their culture and their very necessary existence and presence on Brazilian soil, moments before.

In this complex field of interpretation, the region of Venda Nova do Imigrante stands out which, with blacks occupying their lands before the arrival of Europeans from Italy, with political propaganda and the exalted discourse of whitening the country, as a way of achieving the much publicized economic progress, this caused the loss of the historical identity of the place, which erased the history of the blacks and there was no way to create a history at the height of the local creation for the blond newcomers.

What can be seen from the research work carried out and written is that the conflicts that are shown between whites and blacks in the municipality of Venda Nova do Imigrante, ES, are determined by the attempt to suppress a history of a people and the absence of another,

respectively. Accepting the previous existence of black individuals in the region and a whole condition of struggle against the adversities that life imposed on them, by force and, later with the Italian occupation and all the advancement that they could add to the city, there would be a sequential historical dimension, absent of conflicts that do not add any values to any of the parties.

The issue of the presence, even of prejudice against blacks, in Brazil, is due to the ideological discourse, in which, in order to justify the dehumanizing condition of slavery against equals, in the sense of understanding that they are human beings, the Catholic Church disseminated the idea that they had no *soul*. By this term, it is understood, they do not think, do not feel, do not abstract; they are things and so they reified a whole group of people, indistinctly.

Everything that still feels resentful and ends in discrimination is the result of an unsurpassed hatred and fear of a cult that proved to be superior in many senses, highlighting the clearing and opening of a wild land, helping it to consolidate itself as a of the 10 (ten) largest economies in the world in a few centuries of existence.

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